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Research Article

Composition And Assessment Of Facial Gel Cleanser From Rooster Comb And Extracts Of Papaya Seed Oil

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this study is to formulate and assess an innovative facial gel cleanser containing papaya seed oil and hyaluronic acid (HA) as a primary ingredient. This gentle, non-foaming cleanser effectively removes impurities, dirt and makeup without stripping the skin of its natural oils. Gel cleansers mainly help in deep cleansing, acne fighting, soothing and moisturizing. This gel cleanser not only cleanses but also nourishes and hydrates the skin. Papaya seed oil's antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties help to soothe and protect the skin. Similarly, hyaluronic acid acts as a powerful antioxidant which deeply moisturizes, plumps, leaving the skin feeling soft, supple and refreshed. Extraction of Carica papaya seed was done by Clevenger apparatus. The papaya seed oil, which was extracted from the seeds of Carica papaya fruit, has been found to possess antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. The oil contains various bioactive compounds like flavonoids, polyphenols, fatty acids which can help to protect against cell damage, inflammation and oxidative stress. The extraction of hyaluronic acid from Gallus gallus domesticus is done by chemical extraction which includes defatting, precipitation, filtration, centrifugation and drying. The hyaluronic acid has antioxidative, moisturizing and skin hydration properties. The facial gel cleanser was formulated containing Carica papaya seed oil and hyaluronic acid from Gallus gallus domesticus. Various formulations were prepared i.e. FGC1 to FGC6 using the extracts in different concentrations and evaluated for certain parameters like physical evaluation, washability, measurement of pH, homogeneity, spreadability, irritancy, grittiness, viscosity, foam ability and antioxidant activity. Results showed that FGC5 was found to be optimum for all evaluation parameters. [2][9]

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INTRODUCTION

COSMETICS

Cosmetics are composed of mixtures of chemical compounds derived from natural sources or synthetically created ones. They have various purposes including personal and skin care. Cosmetics are natural or synthetic products that are used to maintain hygiene and include externally applied products used to enhance appearance. They are pharmaceutical products that are used for improving skin appearance and body odour. A cosmetic is an item intended to be rubbed, poured, sprinkled or sprayed on, introduced into or otherwise applied to the human body or any part thereof for cleansing, beautifying, promoting attractiveness or altering appearance. These products are available in various forms like lotions, gels, creams, powders etc. They are designed for skin care and used for cleansing, protecting, exfoliating and moisturizing the skin.

Uses of various cosmetics

- Cosmetics are used as a cleansing, moisturizing and beautifying agent.
- They help in enhancing attractiveness of the body
- They help in altering the appearance of the body without affecting its functions.
- Acne, wrinkles, dark circles under eyes and other skin imperfections are treated or repaired by cosmetics.
- It is designed to enhance one's appearance can be used to conceal blemishes, enhance natural features, or add colour to a person's face.

CLEANSER

Cleanser is the products which are used to cleanse face without drying it out. They are very helpful in removing dirt, oil and provide moisture to the dry skin. It is found to be equally good for all skin type. The term cleanser refers to the product that cleans or removes dirt and other substances. A cleanser dissolves away excess oil makeup and grime from your face. Cleanser does the vital job of keeping

skin clean, germ free smooth and fresh and moisturizes the horny layer without any harshness to the skin. There are many types of cleansers that are produced with a specific objective. Types of cleanser are gel cleansers, cream cleansers, oil cleansers, foam cleansers, clay cleansers, powder cleansers, micellar cleansers.

FACIAL GEL CLEANSER

Gel cleansers is good for eliminating surface oil and acne-causing bacteria as well as giving the skin a deeper clean. This cleanser will work to clear away impurities and prevent future breakouts. They are activated by water, so start by dampening the product in your hands with some water. Then proceed to foam up your gel cleanser using gentle circular massaging motions onto your face for a thorough clean. Rinse off with warm water. Gel cleanser is a different texture than foaming cleanser and are usually thicker and provide a small amount of foaming. They provide a lighter cleaning experience, which makes them ideal for sensitive skin type. It clears and pores without stripping them of your normal skin oil. Many gel cleansers have a cooling and refreshing formula which can soothe your skin. Facial gel cleanser is a great way to start and end your day and ensure that your skin is clean. [2]

FUNCTION OF GEL CLEANSER

- **Cleansing:** Removes dirt, oil, makeup, and impurities from skin.
- **Foaming:** Creates a rich lather that helps to lift and remove impurities.
- **Moisturizing:** Hydrates the skin and leaving it feeling soft and supple.
- **Exfoliating:** Removes dead skin cells, revealing brighter and makes smoother skin.
- **Antibacterial:** Helps control the growth of harmful bacteria on skin.
- **Anti-inflammatory:** Reduces redness and swelling in skin.

- **Antioxidant:** Protects skin from environmental stressors and damage caused by free radicals.
- **Prepares skin for further products:** Allows for better absorption of subsequent skincare products.
- **Eliminate acne-causing bacteria:** Gel cleansers can provide a deeper clean than other types of cleansers.
- **The cleanser will work to clear away impurities,** prevent future breakouts and also reduce scarring.

ADVANTAGES

- **Deep cleansing** Gel cleansers can unclog pores and remove dirt and excess oil without irritating the skin.
- **Acne fighting gel cleansers** can treat bacterial acne with their antiseptic qualities. they can also help to prevent future breakouts.
- **Extra hydrating:** A Gentle gel formula can help keep your pores clear and provide hydration without leaving any residue behind.
- **Softens skin:** Face gels can hydrate your skin while also making it look bright, and clean.
- **Balancing:** gel cleansers cleanse the skin without disrupting its nature moisture balance.
- **Exfoliating face gel cleanses,** detoxicates, and improves the skin qualities.
- **Removing makeup** Gel cleansers can soften and dissolve makeup, making it easy to remove.
- **It provides nutrients to the deeper layers of the skin.** Gel cleansers are clear and have a gel-like consistency, and are ideal for oily or acne-prone skin.
- **It helps reduce the appearance of acne scars and increasing collagen production.**
- **Eliminates surface oil and acne-causing bacteria** as well as giving the skin a deeper clean.
- **Fight ageing problems** that is the blood circulation stimulates and boosts the face and it helps to fight ageing issues. [8]

PLANT PROFILE

Carica Papaya

Carica papaya is species of fruit-bearing plants and belong to the family known as Caricaceae. It was first domesticated in Mesoamerica, within modern-day southern Mexico and Central America. The papaya is a small, sparsely branched tree, usually with a single stem growing from 5 to 10 m (16 to 33 ft.) tall, with spirally arranged leaves confined to the top of the trunk. The plant is cultivated in Sri Lanka, Tanzania, Hawaii, and Florida. Carica papaya seeds are high in vitamin C, contain antioxidants such as phenolic compounds and flavonoids. Incorporating papaya seed extract or oil into skincare formulations may help combat signs of aging and environmental damage. Papaya seed oil is rich in moisturizing fatty acids, such as oleic acid and linoleic acid, which can help hydrate and nourish the skin. It is often used in moisturizers, creams, and lotions to provide long-lasting hydration and improve skin texture.[4]

DISADVANTAGES

- Gel cleanser not effective for removing makeup or sunscreen
- May be too drying for dry skin
- May leave a residue

APPLICATION

- **Facial gel cleansers** remove dirt, makeup, sunscreen, pollution, and dead skin cells from the skin. They also help to exfoliate the top layer of skin.
- **Unclog pores:** Larger pores are more likely to get clogged with oil and impurities.
- **Remove excess oil:** Gel cleansers can remove excess oil without drying out the skin or leaving a greasy residue.

Fig no 1 Papaya seed

Family: Caricaceae Genus: Carica.

Species: Cariappa

ANIMAL PROFILE

Gallus gallus domesticus is the scientific name for the domestic chicken. *Gallus gallus domesticus* are thought to have been domesticated from wild junglefowls in Southeast Asia. Hyaluronic acid (HA) is a linear, non-sulfated polysaccharide mostly extracted from rooster comb.[26] Hyaluronic acid, a sugar molecule found in chicken combs, can help keep human skin moist and elastic. It's a key ingredient in skin care products because it hydrates the skin and reduces the appearance of wrinkles. Also, its antioxidants and anti-inflammatory properties accelerate the formation of newer skin cells and it helps to protect the skin from UV radiation, which can cause premature aging. [26]

Family: Phasianidae Genus: Gallus

Species: *Gallus gallus domesticus*

Fig no 2 Gallus Gallus domesticus

METHODOLOGY

Preparation and extraction

1. Preparation and extraction of *Carica papaya* seed oil by Clevenger apparatus

The fresh papaya seed were initially washed and then dried under shade for 5 to 10 days and then powdered [17]. The powder sample was weighed and stored in air tight container and perform extraction using Clevenger apparatus.[23]

- 300ml of water was added into the round bottom flask of Clevenger apparatus. 50g of powdered papaya seed was added to the flask and fitted into the Clevenger extractor and allowed to run the apparatus for 6 hours at 40°C.
- The mixture in the set-up was heated and vapor produced was subsequently condensed by water flowing in and out of the condenser. The supernatant layer formed is the papaya seed oil and the down layer is water
- At the end of extraction, we can easily separate the oil. The process was continued until a sufficient amount of papaya seed oil was obtained.

2. Preparation and extraction of hyaluronic acid from *Gallus gallus domesticus*

The rooster comb was separated from hen and washed using normal water to remove dirt and dust and then stored it in an ice box. The extraction of hyaluronic acid from rooster comb is done by chemical extraction which include defatting, precipitation, filtration, centrifugation, desiccation.[19][26]

- Grounded 125g of frozen rooster combs was and placed in 250ml of acetone in a refrigerator to remove fat in it. After 2 h, the acetone was drained and fresh acetone was added. This was repeated 10 times.
- After the last extraction and draining, the remaining acetone was evaporated in a stream of air. 20g of dried and defatted rooster combs was obtained.
- This rooster combs were extracted ten times with 250ml of 5% sodium acetate solution at every 2 h interval. Each time the viscous fluid was collected by squeezing through a

cotton cloth and rooster comb residue was discarded.

- Add 375 ml of ethanol, the precipitate was centrifuged, and dissolved in 5% sodium acetate solution, and centrifuged again. Impurities such as protein were removed from the supernatant solution by shaking it with 25 ml chloroform for four times. The solution was precipitated with ethanol again and then the precipitate was dried using desiccator. The dried hyaluronic acid was collected.

FORMULATION OF FACIAL GEL CLEANSER

Phase A:

Xanthan gum was dispersed in distilled water with continuous stirring and kept the beaker aside to swell the xanthan gum to form a gel.

Phase B:

To distilled water, required quantity of Phenoxyethanol and Benzyl Alcohol was dissolved by heating on water bath and then the solution was cooled. Propylene glycol, Sodium cocoyl glutamate, Disodium lauryl sulfosuccinate and Cocamidopropyl betaine was added into it.

Phase C:

Further required quantities of extracts were homogenized and both mixtures were then added into xanthan gum gel base with continuous stirring. Triethanolamine was added drop wise to the formulation for the adjustment of required skin pH and to obtain the gel of required consistency. [1,32]

PREPARATION OF FACIAL GEL CLEANSER:

In this study, six formulations were prepared. These preparations are denoted as FGC1, FGC2, FGC3, FGC4, FGC5, and FGC6.

Table no 1 Formulation of facial gel cleanser

Composition of facial gel cleanser	FGC1 %w/w	FGC2 %w/w	FGC3 %w/w	FGC4 %w/w	FGC5 %w/w	FGC6 %w/w
Papaya seed oil	0.5	0.75	2	1	1.5	1.75
Hyaluronic acid	2	1.75	0.5	1.5	1	0.75
Disodium lauryl sulfosuccinate	2	2	2	2	2	2
Cocamidopropyl Betaine	1	1	1	1	1	1
Xanthan gum	1	1	1	1	1	1
Sodium cocoyl glutamate	2	2	2	2	2	2
Propylene glycol	2	2	2	2	2	2
Triethanolamine	2	2	2	2	2	2
Phenoxyethanol	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Benzyl alcohol	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Rose oil(drops)	q. s					
Distilled Water q.s	q. s					

EVALUATION

Physical evaluation

The physical properties such as appearance, colour and consistency were determined visually. The physical appearance of a facial gel cleanser is an important aspect of its overall quality and acceptability. [22]

Washability

The washability of a facial gel cleanser can be evaluated through a series of tests that assess the ability to be easily rinsed off the skin without leaving any residue. Washing can be done by rinsing the substrate with water using a massaging motion.[2][11]

Measurement of pH

pH of the facial gel cleanser is important to evaluate as it affects the skin natural pH balance

and causes irritation. Calibrate the pH meter properly with buffer solutions before measuring the sample. Measure the pH by inserting the pH electrode in to the gel solution and record the value. Facial gel cleanser was measured by using a calibrated pH meter at constant temperature and average pH is calculated.[2][11]

Homogeneity

The formulation is set on a Container and homogeneity was tested by visual inspection. Visual evaluation includes Evaluation of appearance by observing the gel cleanser's colour, clarity and consistency in transparent container.[10]

Spreadability

The formulation of gel was placed over one of the slides. The other slide was placed on the top of the gel, such that the gel was sandwiched between the two slides. The spread ability is expressed in terms of time in occupied by a distance of 6 cm the slide. The weight of 100gm was placed on the upper slide, so that the gel between the two slides was pressed evenly to a thin layer. The weight was removed and the excess of the gel adhering to the slides was scrapped off. The two slide in position were fixed to stand without slightest disturbance and in such a way that only the upper slide to slip off freely by the force of weight tied to it. The weight of 20 gram was carefully attached to the upper slide. The time taken for the upper slide to travel the distance of 6 cm and separated away from the lower slide under the influence of the weight was noted. The experiment was repeated three times on both formulated gels. Spread ability was calculated by using the following formula,[2][21][11]

Irritancy test

Where,

$$S=M \times L / T$$

S-Spread ability

M-Weight on the upper slide (20gm) L-Length of the glass (6.5cm)

T-Time in sec [4]

The irritancy of a facial gel cleanser can be evaluated through various test these includes. Patch tests in which the gel was applied on left hand dorsal side surface of 1sq.cm and observed in equal intervals up to 24hrs for irritancy, redness and oedema.[10]

Grittiness

The grittiness of a facial gel cleanser refers to the principle of presence of particles or grains that can cause a rough or abrasive sensation on the skin. Test procedure includes samples preparation of gel cleanser in sufficient amount and then visually inspect the cleanser for any visible particles then perform touch test by applying a small amount of gel cleanser to the sensitive area of skin.[10]

Viscosity

The viscosity of a facial gel cleanser is important physical property that affects its texture, spread ability. The value of viscosity is recorded in centipoise (cP) the viscosity of facial gel cleanser was determined by using digital Brookfield viscometer. 50ml of gel cleanser is taken into 100ml of beaker and spindle 64 attached to the viscometer. Then it dipped into the beaker, adjust the speed into 100rpm and record the viscosity reading. [10][24]

Foam ability

The foam ability of facial gel cleanser is an important property that effects its cleaning efficacy. Small amount of gel has been taken and suitable foam generation method is selected. Sample is added into a measuring cylinder containing water. Initial volume was noted, cylinder was shaken for ten times and the final volume was noted. Observe and record the foam stability over a specified time period.[2]

FTIR (fourier transform infrared) spectroscopy

When infrared radiation passes through a sample, some of the radiation is absorbed and radiation that passes through the sample is recorded [9]. FTIR is

the preferred method of infrared spectroscopy for several reasons:

- It does not destroy the sample.
- It is faster than older techniques.
- It is significantly sensitive and precise.

Based on the FTIR spectrum, identify the presence of key ingredient such as surfactants, moisturizers and preservatives. It determines the level of purity or contamination in the sample. It compares the spectrum to that of a standard or reference material to evaluate the products authenticity or consistency [9]. Some common functional groups and their corresponding FTIR spectral regions are:

- Hydroxyl group (-OH): 3500-3200 cm^{-1}
- Carboxyl group (-COOH): 1700-1500 cm^{-1}
- Carbonyl (-C=O): 1800-1600 cm^{-1}

Analysis of antioxidant activity

A standard solution of ascorbic acid was prepared in the concentration of 2 mg/ml in methanol. The standard calibration curve was obtained using different working standards and was made up of 3ml with methanol. DPPH (2, 2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) solution (500 μ l) was then added

and mixed vigorously. Similar steps were followed for the extract. The reaction mixture was incubated for about 45min in dark condition and absorbance was measured at 517 nm using spectrophotometer. The standard curve was obtained using ascorbic acid [2][14]. Antioxidant activity was expressed as percent Scavenging of DPPH and it was calculated by using formula:[25]

Where,

$$\% \text{ Scavenging capacity of DPPH} = (A_0 - A_1)/A_0 \times 100$$

A₀ = absorbance of control A₁ = Absorbance of sample

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Physical evaluation

The physical properties such as appearance, colour and consistency of the prepared facial gel cleanser are visually tested. Gel cleanser formulation was white viscous gel preparation with a smooth homogenous texture and glossy appearance. Consistency and appearance were found to be good. Also, both characteristics was found to be appreciable in formulation FGC5.

Formulation	FGC 1	FGC 2	FGC 3	FGC 4	FGC 5	FGC 6
Result	Good	Good	Good	Good	Good	Good

Washability

The washability of prepared facial gel cleanser was tested and it was found to be easily washable.

Formulation	FGC 1	FGC 2	FGC 3	FGC 4	FGC 5	FGC 6
Result	Easily washable					

Measurement of pH

The pH of gel cleanser was found to be satisfactory and it is in the range of 5.5 to 5.8 which is most

suitable for skin. By comparing all prepared formulations, FGC5 formulation found to have better.

Formulation	FGC 1	FGC 2	FGC 3	FGC 4	FGC 5	FGC 6
Result	4.9	5.2	5.4	5.6	5.75	6.02

Homogeneity

Under visual inspection of the prepared formulation indicates no lumps or aggregate

presents. And the formulation is found to have uniform colour dispersion and free from any particles.

Formulation	FGC 1	FGC 2	FGC 3	FGC 4	FGC 5	FGC 6
Result	Homogenous	Homogenous	Homogenous	Homogenous	Homogenous	Homogenous

Spreadability

The value of Spread ability indicate that the gel is easily spreadable by small amount of shear. From

the result of evaluation, it shows that FGC5 given the higher percentage of spread ability compared to other formulation.

Formulation	FGC 1	FGC 2	FGC 3	FGC 4	FGC 5	FGC 6
Result	1.8cm	2.1cm	2.3cm	2.5cm	2.6cm	2.8cm

Irritancy test

The irritancy test was performed and the facial gel cleanser did not cause any skin irritation or reactions.

Formulation	FGC 1	FGC 2	FGC 3	FGC 4	FGC 5	FGC 6
Result	No Irritation					

Grittiness

The gel cleanser is smooth and free of grittiness, indicating a uniform and consistent texture.

Formulation	FGC 1	FGC 2	FGC 3	FGC 4	FGC 5	FGC 6
Result	No Gritty Particles					

Viscosity

The viscosity measurement was performed and recorded using Brookfield viscometer. The

viscosity was recorded for 6 different concentrated formulations. The viscosity of FGC5 was found to have appropriate viscosity.

Formulation	FGC 1	FGC 2	FGC 3	FGC 4	FGC 5	FGC 6
Result	15201cp	13105cp	11894cp	11071cp	10600cp	9895cp

Foam ability

The foam ability of gel cleanser is performed and found that FGC5 exhibits moderate foaming

performance (provides a small amount of foam) and acceptable foam stability.

Formulation	FGC 1	FGC 2	FGC 3	FGC 4	FGC 5	FGC 6
Result	Passed	Passed	Passed	Passed	Passed	Passed

FTIR

IR radiation passes through the sample, some of the radiation is absorbed. The radiation that passes through the sample is recorded. The FTIR spectrum of the facial gel cleanser suggests that it

contains a blend of Carica papaya oil and hyaluronic acid, as evidenced by the presence of hydroxyl (OH) and carboxyl (COOH) functional groups.

Peak number	X axis (cm ⁻¹)	Y axis (%T)
1	3350.04	53.59
2	1631.51	69.55

Fig no 3 FTIR Spectrum of Facial Gel Cleanser

Antioxidant activity

Antioxidant activity of Carica Papaya seed oil and hyaluronic acid

Conc.(µg/ml)	Ascorbic acid		Papaya seed oil		Hyaluronic acid	
	Absorbance	RSA (%)	Absorbance	RSA (%)	Absorbance	RSA (%)
20	0.475	50.3	0.524	45.1	0.082	30.5
40	0.341	64.3	0.408	57.2	0.086	27.1
60	0.266	72.2	0.390	59.01	0.081	31.3
80	0.191	80.2	0.241	74.7	0.089	24.5
100	0.149	84.6	0.296	69.1	0.084	28.8
200	0.095	90.03	0.245	74.3	0.080	35.9
Control	0.955		0.955		0.118	

Antioxidant Activity of Extracts

Antioxidant activity of formulation

Formulations	Absorbance	Percentage (%)
FGC1	0.085	65.1
FGC2	0.154	36.6
FGC3	0.132	45.6
FGC4	0.053	78.1
FGC5	0.038	84.3
FGC6	0.104	57.2
Control	0.243	

CONCLUSION

The facial gel cleanser prepared from the extracts of rooster comb and papaya seed oil having antioxidant properties. The hyaluronic acid was extracted from the Gallus Gallus Domesticus and papaya seed oil was extracted from Carica Papaya. Papaya seed oil help to protect the skin from oxidative stress caused by the free radicles and hyaluronic acid helps to retain the moisture and smoothen the skin. The facial gel cleanser is a facial care product which is used to remove makeup, skin care product residue, dirt, sweat, and prevent the skin infection like acne. It helps to prevent clogged pores, filth accumulation and protect the skin from oxidative stress. It provides long lasting hydration and plumps the skin for a more youthful appearance. Six gel cleanser formulations (FGC1-6) were evaluated, showing distinct differences. All were easy to wash off without residue. Phytochemical screening revealed various compounds, including antioxidants. FGC3 and FGC5 had similar appearances, while FGC4 and FGC5 had optimal pH levels (5.5-5.8) for skin. FGC5 also showed optimal viscosity (10600 Cp) and antioxidant activity (confirmed by FTIR). Overall, FGC5 was identified as the best formulation The seed oil of Carica papaya was successfully extracted using water as a solvent in a Clevenger apparatus and hyaluronic acid was extracted from rooster comb of hen. In the case of hyaluronic acid, it also acts as powerful antioxidant and helps to retain moisture and soothe the skin. Hyaluronic acid is

typically derived from either rooster combs or fermentation. It's a key ingredient in skin care products because it hydrates the skin and reduces the appearance of wrinkles. By combining the natural benefits of papaya seed oil and hyaluronic acid, our formula offers a gentle and effective solution for healthy-looking skin. Thus, from the studies, we discovered that FGC5 is the best formulation of Facial gel cleanser based on physical and chemical evaluation. Hence antioxidant activity was evaluated, and the FGC5 formulation exhibited significant antioxidant properties. All the six formulations were evaluated for various parameters like physical evaluation, washability, measurement of pH, homogeneity, Spreadability, irritancy, grittiness, viscosity and foam ability studies. The above formulations exhibiting no skin irritation or adverse reactions, making them suitable

REFERENCE

1. Raslamol K., Anjitha M. B., Ashitha C. M., Sanija Sivan U., Shahana P. M. and S. Krishna- Bigels: The Future of Cosmetics Delivery on volume 10, Issue 6, 23 May 2024, Page No:181-186.
2. Sujith S Nair, Athira M Raveendran, Abhay krishna-Preparation and evaluation of herbal wash gel on Volume 12, Issue 7, 15 July 2023, Page No:1590-1601.
3. Callejas-Quijada Graciela Escobar-Chavez Jose Jaun, Compos-Lozada Gieraldin Perez-Marroquin Xochitl Alejandra and Aguirre-alvarez Gabriel- Extraction of Hyaluronic

- acid on Volume 15, Issue 16, 23 August 2023, Page no: 523-529.
4. Patricia Galvez-Martin, Cristina Sotho-Fernandez, Jessica Romeo-Rueda, Jesus Cabanas, Anna Torrent, Glorial Castells and Daniel Martinus-Puig - A Novel Hyaluronic Acid Matrix Ingredient with Regenerative, Anti-Aging and Antioxidant Capacity on Volume 24, Issue 5, 1 March 2023, Page no: 312-317.
 6. Nastaran Tabari Shahandasht, Marzieh Bolandi, Majid Rahmati, Moslem Jafarisani - Comparison of physicochemical and rheological characteristics of hyaluronic acid extracted from rooster comb using different methods on Volume 19, Issue 127, 1 September 2022, Page no: 79-89.
 7. Joachim M. Dotto, Siri A Abihudi - Nutraceutical value of Carica papaya: A review on vol 13, Issue 3, 13 September 2021, page no: 766-787.
 8. Varsha Singh, Aleza Risvi, Udaivir Singh Sara - Standardization and phytochemical screening of Carica papaya seeds, volume 14, Issue 9, 2021, Page no: 4540-4546.
 9. Zoe Diana Draelos, Isabel Diaz, Jin Namkoong, Joanna Wu, Thomas Boyd - Efficacy evaluation of a topical hyaluronic acid serum in facial photoaging on volume 7, issue 11, 10 June 2021, page no: 1385-1394.
 10. Rohini P. Gawade, Shamal L. Chinke, Prashant S. Alegaonkar - Polymers in cosmetics on volume, Issue 4, 05 June 2020, Page no: 545-565.
 11. Prasanna Durgam, Pallavi Vadlamudi, Ramarao Nadendla - Formulation and evaluation of multi-herbal face wash gel, volume 9, Issue 5, 01 May 2020, Page no: 916-925.
 12. Dnyanshwar S. Solanki, Prof. Dattatray Sagarule, Shrikrushna Subhash Unhale, Quazi Bilal Ansar, Prof. Chitte and Prof. Dr. K. R. Biyani - Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Instant Whitening Face Wash on Volume 9, Issue 5, 01 May 2020, Page No: 2541-2557.
 13. Nandini G, Gopenath Ts, Nagalambika Prasad, Murugesan Kathikeyan, Ashok Gnanasekaran, Ranjith Ms, Pradeep Palanisamy, Kanthesh M Basalingappa - phytochemical analysis and antioxidant properties of leaf extracts of Carica Papaya on volume 13, issue 11, 22 August 2020, page no: 58-62
 14. Vibha Devi, Shabina Khanam - Development of generalized and simplified models for supercritical fluid extraction: Case study of papaya (Carica papaya) seed oil on Volume 150, issue 10, 07 October 2019, Page no: 341-358.
 15. S. L. Sija, A. S. Athulya, M. R. Mahia, Ashok Vidhya - Antioxidant and Antimicrobial Activity of Different Plant Parts of Anacardium occidentale L. and Mangifera indica L.: Comparative Study on Volume 11, Issue 4, 14 July 2019, Page No: 111-115.
 16. Fatma Zuhrotun Nisa, Mary Astuti, Sofia Mubarika Haryana, Agnes Murdiati - Antioxidant activity and total flavonoid of carica papaya leaves with different varieties, maturity and solvent on Volume 39, Issue 1, 20 Feb 2019, Page no: 54-59.
 17. Chin Xuan Tan, Seok Tyung Tan, Seok Shin Tan - An overview of papaya seed oil extraction method on Volume 55, Issue 4, 24 October 2019, Page no: 1506-1514
 18. Burla Sunitha, Venkatta Seshamamba, P. Malati, A. Nancy Grace Ruth, A. Swetha Mallika and Vivek Sharma - Studies on physicochemical properties and proximate analysis of Carica papaya seed on Volume 7, Issue 6, 8 May 2018, Page no: 1514-1519.
 19. Cevriye Kalkandelen; Sena Su; Elif Saatcioglu; Oguzhan Gunduz - Hyaluronic

- Acid Production and Analysis from Rooster Comb on Volume 6 ,Issue 110,12 July 2017,Page No 42-49.
20. Briyoj, Anup Maiti, Laliteshwar Pratap Singh – Formulation and evaluation of polyherbal gel on volume 3, issue 8, 17 May 2017, page no:11-14.
 21. Priyanka Jangalrao Jadhav, Abhyang Shree Nandkumar Mane, Sagar Suresh Gilda, Vinayak Balu Kumbhar, Monali Bharat Jadhav, Amruta Avinash Ghadge – Formulation and Evaluation of Poly Herbal Anti-Acne Face Wash Gel, Volume 5, Issue 7,19 June 2016, Page No:1184-90.
 22. Sowmya .K V , Darsika. C, X . Fathima Grace, Shanmuganathan – Formulation and Evaluation of a Polyherbal Face Wash Gel, Volume 4, Issue 6, 09 May 2015, Page No:585- 588.
 23. Y.M. Li, N. Su, H.Q. Yang, X.P. Bai, Q.X. Zhu, H.X. Liu and J.Q. Li-Extraction and properties of carica papaya seed oil on Volume 7, Issue 10,5 April 2015, Page no:773-779.
 24. Zieba Malgorzata, Klimazewaska Emilia, Malysa Anna, Olga Jagiello, Gruszczynska Marlena, Gajowiak Maja – physicochemical and usage properties of facial cleansing gels with the addition of the selected active component, volume 4, issue 21, 4 June 2015, page no:134-143.
 25. Idha Kusumawati, Gunawan Indrayanto-Natural Antioxidants in Cosmetics on volume 40, Issue 1, 27 June 2013, Page no: 485-505
 26. P. Saranraj,M.A Naidu-Hyalauroic acid production and its application on Volume 4,Issue 5, 3 October 2013,Page no:853-859.
 27. Eleni papakonstantinou Michael Roth, George Karakiulakis-Hyaluronic acid: a key molecule in skin ageing on vol 4, Issue 3, 1 July 2012, Page no: 253-258.
 28. Yee Kwang Ang, Winne CM Sia, Hock Eng Khoo, Hip Seng Yim-Antioxidant potential of Carica Papaya seed on Volume1, Issue1,16 November 2012, Page No:11-15.
 29. Afolabi,I.S Ofobrukmeta K-Physiochemical and nutritional qualities of carica papaya seed products on Volume 5, Issue 14, 19 April 2011,Page no:3113-3117.
 30. Vijay Kothari,Sriram Seshadri- Antioxidant activity of seed extracts of squamosa and carica papaya on Volume 40, Issue 4, 20 July 2010, Page no:403-407.
 31. Robert Samuelsson, Jan Burvall, Raida Jirjis- Comparison of different methods for determination of moisture content biomass, volume 30, Issue 11, November 2006, Page no:929-934.
 32. Zoe Kececioglu Draelos MD- Cosmetics: An overview on volume 7, Issue 2, March –April 1995, Page no:45-64.
 33. P.P Sharma -Formulation Manufacturing and Quality control on Volume 5, Issue 6, Page no:80-243.

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